

Epidemiology of Covid-19 Outbreak in Jigawa State, Northwest Nigeria

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Received 20 December, 2023, Accepted 15 January, 2024, Published 10 February 2024

The novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) caused a global pandemic in December 2019. The epidemiology of the COVID-19 in Jigawa State was described to generate information that guided our planning and response. A descriptive cross-sectional study of COVID-19 was conducted using Jigawa State surveillance data from April 19, 2020, through December 31, 2021. A real-time Polymerase Chain Reaction-based confirmatory testing for COVID-19 (RT-PCR) was used. Cumulative incidence (CI) and case fatality rate (CFR) were the main outcomes. Frequencies, proportions, mean and standard deviation (SD) of sociodemographic and outcome variables was computed. Of the 522 patients with complete clinical outcome information, 18 (3.45%) of them died. The overall CI and CFR were 7.0 per 100,000 population and 3.4%, respectively. The highest proportion of COVID-19 cases and deaths were recorded in persons aged 10–19 years (25.1%) and 0-9 years (15.8%), respectively, while mean age \pm S.D was 31 ± 17 years. Males were (70.7%) confirmed cases and CFR was 3.5%. Dutse LGA had the highest CI of 69.9 per 100,000 populations. CFR among Almajiris was 6%. About 96.2% of cases had their data missing on educational status. In conclusion, evidence from this study showed that males; active age group were found to have a high infection and death rates. Surveillance should be intensified at schools and commercial places. Jigawa State Government should promote policies that reduce interaction with confirmed or suspected cases at the state, LGA, and community levels by the use NCDC's guidelines. Further research should be conducted for better understanding of the disease.

Keywords: Coronavirus, COVID-19, Epidemiology, Jigawa, Nigeria, Outbreak, Pandemic

INTRODUCTION

In December 2019, an incident of pneumonia with an unknown cause was discovered in Wuhan, the capital of Hubei Province, China (Bogoch et al., 2020 \$ Guan et al.,

2019). A genomic sequencing revealed a novel coronavirus as the potential etiological agent (Gebru, et al., 2021). On 30th January 2020, the WHO announced the approved name of the virus as Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS- CoV-2) and the disease as Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) (Lai et al., 2019). The disease was declared an outbreak

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of Public Health Emergency of International Concern on 30 January 2020 by the WHO Director General (Sohrabi et al., 2021). Over 79 million cases and 1.7 million deaths were recorded throughout the world in December 2020 (WHO, 2020). Similarly, over 1.9 million cases and 43,000 mortalities were recorded in Africa. As at 30/12/2021, Nigeria recorded 256,958 cases and 3,144 deaths among which 669 cases and 18 deaths were from Jigawa State (NCDC, 2022). The index case for Jigawa State was recorded on April 19, 2020, a returning traveler from Lagos detected by Point of Entry (PoE) screening staff at the Kano-Jigawa border.

COVID-19 affects important demographic age groups thus having a severe impact on the productivity of the workforce. For example, persons below the age of 50 have moderate to severe infections at a rate of 10 to 15% (Manivannan et al., 2021, Ejikeme et al., 2020). In addition, males were reported to have higher infection

rates (Ejikeme et al., 2020) Urban settings are more vulnerable to higher transmission of SARS-COV2 owing to their nature of high socio-economic activities (Lee et al., 2021). Understanding the epidemiology of the disease in Jigawa State and the pattern of transmission will inform appropriate state-specific public health control measures. We conducted a descriptive cross-sectional study to describe the epidemiology of COVID-19 confirmed cases in Jigawa State.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study Area

Jigawa State, located in the north-western geopolitical zone of Nigeria, has twenty-seven local government areas and Dutse is the capital. It shares boundary with

Figure 1: Geographical distribution of COVID-19 cases by LGAs, Jigawa State, April 19, 2020- December 31, 2021

Kano State to the west from where a huge number of *Almajiris* (An itinerant student at an Islamic school in northern Nigeria) were deported. Shares borders with Katsina State to the north-west, Bauchi State to the south-east, and Yobe State to the north-east. It also shares international boundary with the Republic of Niger to the north. The State occupies an area of 23,509.6 square kilometers and has a projected population of 7,499,100 people (2022 projected figure from 2006 census) (NPC, 2021). About 50.4% of the population of Jigawa State are male, and 49.6% are female; additionally, the population is made up of 47.3% of

children (0–14 years), 49.5% of adults (15–64 years), and 3.2% of the elderly (65 years and older), respectively (Lai et al., 2019).

Data Generation

In an advent of covid-19 outbreak, rapid response teams were formed by collaboration of the Jigawa State Ministry of Health, Jigawa State Primary Healthcare Agency, and Nigerian Centre for Disease Control (NCDC), World Health Organization and other partners in the state to address the outbreak as it started. The 2014 Ebola out-

-break in Nigeria served as the inspiration for SORMAS, a mobile and web-based platform and database. It was introduced to aid the Integrated Disease Surveillance and Response (IDSR) system. Following the 2014 Ebola outbreak, NCDC adopted SORMAS. Today, SORMAS is utilized throughout Nigeria. COVID-19 component was incorporated following the pandemic and is used by some countries in the world (Sohrabi et al., 2020, World Health Organization. 2020). Data entry for immediate case-based surveillance is carried out at medical facilities, laboratories, and by field surveillance officers. Data quality, timeliness, and completeness were responsibility of the State Epidemiologist, NCDC Surveillance Support Officer, and Data Clerk. Within the first four days of case identification, between 80% and 90% of the data on all confirmed cases are transferred to SORMAS and updated.

Study Subjects

The study subjects included all confirmed COVID-19 cases of all ages in Jigawa State from 19 April 2020 to 31 December 2021, who reside in 27 the Local Government Areas. The subject also comprised of the *Almajiris* who were deported from other states.

Study Design

We retrospectively reviewed COVID-19 surveillance data from April 19, 2020, through December 31, 2021, to characterize the outbreak in terms of person, place and time.

Study Population and Data Collection

The study population involved persons infected with SARS-CoV-2 virus and cases were investigated and captured on SORMAS during the study period. Data were collected from suspected cases that met up with the standard case definition of COVID-19 (as provided by the NCDC and WHO) and were detected by the surveillance system in Jigawa State. We collected two Nasopharyngeal (NP) and Oro-pharyngeal swabs from each suspected COVID-19 patient, stored in Viral Transport Media (VTM) and transported to the reference laboratories for real-time PCR (qPCR) analyses.

Case Definition and Contact Persons

We defined suspected, confirmed, and probable cases using NCDC COVID-19 surveillance guidelines (NCDC. 2021). A suspected case was any person presenting with fever, cough, or difficulty in breathing, and who within 14 days before the onset of illness had any of the following exposures: a) history of travel to any high-risk country (consistently reporting increased number of COVID-19

cases) with widespread community transmission of SARS-CoV-2. OR b) close contact with a confirmed case of COVID-19. OR c) exposure to a health care facility where COVID-19 case(s) have been reported. A probable case was any suspected case a) For whom testing for COVID-19 presents an indeterminate test result(s) OR b) For whom testing was positive on a pan-coronavirus assay OR c) Where samples were not collected before the demise of a suspect case. A confirmed case was any person with laboratory confirmation of SARS-CoV-2 infection with or without signs and symptoms (NCDC, 2020).

DATA SOURCE

The data for this study was obtained from the Surveillance Outbreak Response Management and Analysis System (SORMAS). It is an open-source real-time mobile eHealth system that deals with digitalization of the Integrated Disease Surveillance and Response hosted by NCDC to and facilitates quick data collection, reporting, processing, and transmission in a two-way fashion (SORMAS 2022). All cases (suspected, confirmed, and probable) of COVID-19 were entered into the software. However, the team used only the record of positive cases of SARS-CoV-2 infection for our study.

Data Management and Analysis

The team analyzed sociodemographic, and outcome (dead or alive) Variables. Data was cleaned and analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics (V26.0) [16] and Microsoft Excel-V2019 for the selected variables. We used Quantum Geographic Information System (QGIS 2.18.5) to display spatial distribution of the cases (QGIS. 2021). We conducted univariate analysis to calculate frequencies, proportions, mean and standard deviation (SD).

Ethical Clearance

We obtained ethical approval from the ethical committee of the Jigawa State Ministry of Health. Identifiers such as Epid numbers and names have been removed to ensure confidentiality. On the SORMAS platform, data is password-protected, securely kept, and accessible only to authorized staff.

RESULTS

A total of 522 confirmed cases were analyzed during the study period. There were 18 deaths giving rise to a case fatality rate (CFR) of 3.4% (Table 1). Mean age of persons who died from COVID-19 was 30.8 (16.7) years

Table 1. Distribution of sociodemographic characteristics, death outcome and case fatality rate of COVID-19 cases in Jigawa State, April 19, 2020 to December 31, 2021

Variables	Clinical outcome among COVID-19 cases		
	Alive (n=504 (%))	Death (n=18 (%))	CFR (n=3.6%)
<i>Sociodemographic Characteristics</i>			
Mean (S.D.) age, years	31.2 (17.0)	30.8 (16.7)	
Age Group, Years			
0-9	19 (3.6)	3 (16.7)	15.8
10-19	131 (25.1)	8 (44.4)	6.1
20-29	128 (24.5)	3 (16.7)	2.3
30-39	89 (17.0)	2 (11.1)	2.3
40-49	62 (11.9)	2 (11.1)	2.2
50-59	40 (7.7)	0 (0.0)	0
60-69	35 (6.7)	0 (0.0)	0
70-79	16 (3.1)	0 (0.0)	0
≥80	2 (0.4)	0 (0.0)	0
Sex			
Male	369 (70.7)	13 (72.2)	3.5
Female	153 (29.3)	5 (27.8)	3.3
Residential Setting			
Rural	136 (26.1)	3 (16.7)	2.2
Urban	386 (73.9)	15 (83.3)	3.9
Education			
Tertiary	6 (1.1)	0 (0.0)	0
Secondary	3 (0.6)	0 (0.0)	0
Primary	4 (0.8)	1 (5.6)	25
Other	2 (0.4)	0 (0.0)	0
None	5 (1.0)	0 (0.0)	0
Missing	502 (96.2)	17 (94.4)	3.4
Occupation			
Businessman /Woman	1 (0.2)	0 (0.0)	0
Farmer	2 (0.4)	0 (0.0)	0
Healthcare worker	2 (0.4)	0 (0.0)	0
Housewife	6 (1.2)	0 (0.0)	0
Missing	491 (94.1)	17 (94.4)	3.5
Other	13 (2.5)	0 (0.0)	0
Pupil /student	4 (0.8)	1 (5.6)	25
Religious leader	1 (0.2)	0 (0.0)	0
Working with animals	1 (0.2)	0 (0.0)	0
Almajiri Status			
<i>Almajiri</i>	117 (22.4)	7 (38.9)	6
<i>Non Almajiri</i>	405 (77.6)	11 (61.1)	2.7

indicated that those living in Urban Setting were 386 (73.9%). Despite the large proportion of missing information on education 502 (96.2%), however, patients

with tertiary education had a higher proportion 6 (1.1%) of COVID-19, while patients with first school leaving certificate had a CFR of 25%. Regarding the occupation,

Table 2: Clinical signs and symptoms of COVID-19 cases in Jigawa state, April 19, 2020 to December 31, 2021

Variables	Alive (n=504 (%))	Death (n=18 (%))	Total (n=522 (%))
No	386 (76.6)	15 (83.3)	401 (76.8)
Yes	110 (21.8)	2 (11.1)	112 (21.5)
Missing	8 (1.6)	1 (5.6)	9 (1.7)
Difficulty in breathing			
No	478 (94.8)	17 (0.0)	495 (94.8)
Yes	1 (0.2)	0 (0.0)	1 (0.2)
Missing	25 (5.0)	0 (0.0)	26 (5.0)
Fatigue			
No	484 (96.0)	17 (94.4)	501 (96.0)
Yes	5 (1.0)	0 (0.0)	5 (1.0)
Missing	15 (3.0)	1 (5.6)	16 (3.1)
Fever			
No	48 (9.5)	2 (11.1)	50 (9.6)
Yes	456 (90.5)	16 (88.9)	472 (90.4)
Headache			
No	205 (4.7)	9 (50.0)	214 (41.0)
Yes	295 (58.5)	9 (50.0)	304 (58.2)
Missing	4 (0.8)	0 (0.0)	4 (0.8)
Rapid breathing			
No	376 (74.6)	12 (66.7)	388 (74.3)
Yes	1 (0.2)	0 (0.0)	1 (0.2)
Missing	127 (25.2)	6 (33.3)	133 (25.5)
Runny nose			
No	486 (96.4)	17 (94.4)	503 (96.4)
Yes	4 (0.8)	0 (0.0)	4 (0.8)
Missing	14 (2.8)	1 (5.6)	15 (2.9)
Sore throat			
No	489 (97.0)	17 (94.4)	506 (96.9)
Yes	1 (0.2)	0 (0.0)	1 (0.2)
Missing	14 (2.8)	1 (5.6)	15 (2.9)
Loss of smell			
No	486 (96.4)	17 (94.4)	503 (96.4)
Yes	18 (3.6)	1 (5.6)	19 (3.6)
Loss of taste			
No	486 (96.4)	17 (94.4)	503 (96.4)
Yes	18 (3.6)	1 (5.6)	19 (3.6)
Pneumonia			
No	478 (94.8)	17 (94.4)	495 (94.8)
Yes	1 (0.2)	0 (0.0)	1 (0.2)
Missing	25 (5.0)	1 (5.6)	26 (5.0)

491 (94.1%) had missing data while other occupation and housewife were 13 (2.6%) and 6 (1.2%) respectively. Of the total cases, *Almajiris* accounted for up to 117 (22.4%) of cases and CFR was 6% among them (Table 1). Regarding the clinical signs and symptoms, fever

(90.5%), headache (58.5%) and cough (21.8%), were the most recorded signs and symptoms. The remaining symptoms such as loss of smell (3.6%), runny nose (0.8%), muscle pain (1.2%) and malaise (0.4%) were rarely recorded (Table 2).

Figure: 2 Epidemic curve showing the number of confirmed COVID-19 cases and Deaths by date of symptoms, Jigawa State, April 19, 2020 to December 31, 2021

In the early months (April, May, and June), the epidemic curve shows a high number of cases in April (51 cases) and peaked in May (94 cases), and the cases dropped sharply in June (19 cases) and continue to decline variably until October (6 cases). It suddenly increased in November (25 cases) and got higher in December (87 cases), and then declined in January 2021 (46 cases). From then, the cases continue to decrease irregularly till June (5 cases). There was a small spike in July (29 cases) and reduction continues with little variations until the little spike in December (24 cases) (Figure 1). The number of deaths increased gradually from April (3 deaths) until May when it peaked (4 deaths). However, it dropped in June (1 death) and July (1 death). There was no death from August through October. The epicurve also shows a slight increase of death in November (2 deaths) and a slight dip in December (1 death) and January 2021 (1 death), followed by a slight increase in February (2 deaths). Afterwards, the number of deaths continued to be zero until October (1 deaths) and no deaths in November till December (2 deaths) (Figure 1).

All twenty-seven Local-Government Areas (LGAs) reported at least one confirmed case of COVID-19 (Figure 2). There was a cluster of cases seen around *Dutse* LGA. The cases sparsely clustered at *Kaugama*, *Kafin-Hausa*, *Buji*, *Birnin kudu*, *Kiyawa* and *Gwaram* LGAs. The cases were sporadically distributed across

other LGAs (Figure 2). Similarly, a spot of random points indicating deaths was clustered around *Dutse* LGA. A few were seen in *Auyo* and *Taura* LGAs (Figure 1).

The overall cumulative incidence (CI) of COVID-19 infection and case fatality rate (CFR) in Jigawa state during the study period was 7.0 per 100 000 population and 3.5 %, respectively (Table 2). *Dutse* LGA (7.0 per 100 000), followed by *Kafin Hausa* (10.4 per 100 000), recorded the highest CI in Jigawa State during the study period. Other LGAs with CI higher than the State figure include *Hadejia* (8.9 per 100 000) and *Buji* (8.3 per 100 000), while *Jahun* (0.3 per 100 000) and *Birniwa* (0.3 per 100 000) recorded the least. Regarding CFR across the various LGAs in the States, *Auyo* and *Taura* recorded the highest figure at 12.5% both, followed by *Kaugama* (7.1%) and *Dutse* (5.0%). However, death was not recorded in the other LGAs (Table 2). The geographical distribution of confirmed COVID-19 cases and death by LGAs is presented in Figure 1.

In general, the CFR from COVID-19 infection increased with decreasing age, reaching its peak at 18.8% among individuals aged 0–9 years. Death in males was slightly higher (CFR=3.7%) than that in females (CFR=3.4%). Similarly, CFR was 4% among those living in urban setting while *Almajiris* had a CFR of 6.4%. on education, 33.3% died among those who had primary school education while individuals whose data were missing

Table 3: Cumulative incidence of COVID-19 and case fatality in Jigawa State, Nigeria, April 19, 2020-December 31, 2021

Variable	Population at risk	Number of COVID-19 cases	Cumulative incidence/100,000 population	Number of deaths from COVID-19	CFR (%)
Auyo	227,400	8	3.5	1	12.5
Birniwa	366,200	1	0.3	0	0
Babura	244,200	4	1.6	0	0
Buji	540,100	45	8.3	0	0
Birnin kudu	167,300	12	7.2	0	0
Dutse	431,800	302	69.9	15	5.0
Gumel	141,300	5	3.5	0	0
Gwaram	258,400	5	1.9	0	0
Gwiwa	182,900	9	4.9	0	0
Gagarawa	194,900	1	0.5	0	0
Guri	466,600	14	3.0	0	0
Garki	221,400	2	0.9	0	0
Hadejia	179,300	16	8.9	0	0
Jahun	395,300	1	0.3	0	0
Kiri kasamma	459,600	18	3.9	0	0
Kafin hausa	221,800	23	10.4	0	0
Kazaure	277,100	8	2.9	0	0
Kiyawa	331,200	2	0.6	0	0
Kaugama	297,400	14	4.7	1	7.1
Malam madori	304,500	1	0.3	0	0
Miga	283,400	5	1.8	0	0
Maigatari	219,900	7	3.2	0	0
Roni	330,900	5	1.5	0	0
Ringim	133,100	2	1.5	0	0
Sule tankarkar	231,800	1	0.4	0	0
Taura	226,700	8	3.5	1	12.5
Yankwashi	164,500	3	1.82	0	0
Total	7,499,100	522	6.96	18	3.45

had 3.5% death (Table 3).

DISCUSSION

The team described the epidemiology of COVID-19 cases and related clinical features and outcomes for Jigawa State from April 19, 2020, to December 31, 2021. For the period of this study, deaths recorded, Cumulative Incidence and a CFR were the major results. The results are intended to guide efficient state-specific responses, particularly considering the lessons learnt during the outbreak response of COVID-19 (Bickley et al., 2021).

The index case of COVID-19 in Jigawa State was recorded on April 19, 2020. The number of cases gradually increased in the early months (April and May) of the outbreak. This finding could be linked to the total lockdown in the country that necessitates people moving to their various states of origin between announcement and implementation (Kishore et al., 2021). Another possible reason may be due to deportation of indigenous *Almajiris* from other states. This is contrary to observed causes of sudden increase in cases from other studies (Hussein et al., 2020). Our study indicates that males are more likely to become infected with SARS-CoV-2 than females. This is consistent with earlier national and global

studies on COVID-19 (Bukola et al., 2020, Elimian et al., 2020, Bwire 2022]. A possible explanation could be males interact more, go out and engage in trade, travels, agriculture, and related activities in the northern patriarchal setting than females and thus, could increase their chances of acquiring SARS-CoV-2 virus. Furthermore, studies showed that hormonal variations and high expression of coronavirus receptors (ACE 2) in males, and males' high drinking and smoking habits compared to females could be why males have more overt clinical manifestations than females (Bwire 2020). Our study also revealed that most people affected were in the younger age group (10-19 years). This could be attributed to high levels of exposure of young age groups in sociocultural and economic activities, requiring them to be more mobile, and therefore having increased exposure. These young individuals often struggle as hawkers, vendors and *Almajiris* etc. They go to schools more, play more, visit playgrounds and markets more than older age groups (Abeya et al. 2022) and thus were more vulnerable to infection (Elimian et al., 2020). This is consistent with earlier findings from Delta state (Ejikeme et al., 2020) and the country at large (Elimian et al., 2020). Additionally, *Almajiris* (most of which were children) contributed to more than one-quarter of the cases.

The analysis of the clinical symptoms of confirmed COVID-19 cases indicated that most patients presented with at least one symptom before testing. The most common signs and symptoms recorded were fever, headache, and cough. A similar study in Lagos (Ejikeme et al., 2020) and China (10) showed a fever and cough to be the commonest symptom of COVID-19 infection. Furthermore, a relatively small proportion of cases with loss of smell and loss of taste among confirmed COVID-19 cases in this study is consistent with available evidence (Faruk et al., 2020). During the first two months of the outbreak, the cases spread to almost every LGA in the State. A cluster of cases was seen in Dutse LGA. This clustering could be due to the concentration of people in the LGA for economic, political, or other reasons, as it is the capital of the State. It could also be due to strong surveillance and the high testing capacity within the state capital. The epicurve suggests a propagated pattern implying community transmission. Similar finding was reported from Oyo State (Bukola et al., 2020). This justifies the government's decision to mandate preventive measures (such as the use of facemasks and hand sanitizers, respiratory etiquette, and observing social distancing) across the state to reduce morbidity and mortality. After Yobe, Kebbi, Zamfara and Kogi, Jigawa is the least most-affected state in terms of recorded confirmed COVID-19 cases and deaths as of July 2022 (NCDC. 2021).

However, the CI of COVID-19 in Nigeria during the study period at 5.6 per 100,000 population (WHO 2020).

is relatively lower than our finding. Moreover, many LGAs reached a CI of at least 1.5 confirmed cases per 100,000 population over a period of the study. However, Dutse LGA had the highest CI which was much higher than that of the entire State. A possible reason for these variations could be due to weaker surveillance across LGAs compared to Dutse LGA (Capital of the State). Another possible explanation might be due to differences in the projected population of LGAs in states, LGA with lesser population documenting a higher CI and vice-versa. For example, Auyo LGA (227,400 population) and Kazaure LGA (277,100 population) each recorded 8 confirmed COVID-19 cases during this study period; but the latter recorded a lower CI (2.89 per 100,000 population) than the former (3.52 per 100,000). Additionally, all the LGAs might not have a similar surveillance strength capacity during the study period, and this might have contributed to the observed findings in terms of the figures of cases for calculating CIs.

Similarly, the CFR of 3.45% in this study is higher than the national figure of 2.8% (WHO 2020) and several other States (NCDC. 2021) which have been hit by the COVID-19 pandemic. There is a variation in CFR across the LGAs ranging from 0.0% in most of the LGAs to 12.5% in Auyo and Taura LGAs. A possible explanation for this finding could also be due to discrepancies in the denominator (number of cases). For instance, Taura, Auyo, and Kaugama have a similar number of recorded deaths, but Auyo and Taura have the same CFR because they have the same denominator (Manivannan et al., 2021).

However, the CFR from Kaugama is lower compared to Taura and Auyo because of the denominator is greater. Equally, Dutse LGA has the highest number of recorded deaths, yet the CFR is lower than the LGAs stated. Furthermore, as cases are potentially underestimated due to weaker surveillance and inadequate testing, it is possible that COVID-19 deaths are underreported as well, especially in areas like Hadejia, where unusual unexplained deaths were reported in May 2020.

In line with the CFR, a higher proportion of deaths from COVID-19 was noted among economically active age groups, indicating that immune system strength may play a greater role than socioeconomic status or occupation. This result could also be explained by poor access to care and health seeking behaviour. Some elderly individuals die outside of hospital and without access to testing; their deaths during the pandemic might not be recognized as being due to COVID-19. It could be probably due to low infection rate of COVID-19 among older age compared to younger age. Evidence shows that infection rate plays a role in the COVID-19 mortality age profile in developing countries (Bukola et al., 2020,

Moreover, this finding contradicts what was found in some other part of the country (Elimian et al., 2020, Mohammed et al., 2021) and globally (Albalawi et al.,

2021, Abraha et al., 2021). Despite the low proportion (3.2%) of the elderly (65 years and older), however, the Jigawa state surveillance system could have detected at least a case.

Hence, weaker surveillance could have been a reason for this result.

Limitations

Our study is limited by the substantial proportion of missing data within some of the sociodemographic characteristics (e.g., Education and Occupation) and clinical (e.g., malaise, rapid breathing, and chills/sweat) variables studied. Some variables were not included in the study because they contained a significant number of unknown values. The discrepancy between the variables on the paper-based case investigation form and the updated variables on SORMAS, the primary electronic reporting platform, was another cause of the missing data. The Primary Healthcare Agency, NCDC, and Jigawa State Ministry of Health worked to guarantee that the SORMAS data was updated. Only 18 deaths were reported in Jigawa State; this was far too few to accurately represent the number of deaths caused by COVID-19 in the state. Thus, a limitation.

Public Health Actions

A specialized Data Quality Improvement Project (DQIP) was started to increase the completeness of the data, because of the high percentage of missing data on some important variables that has motivated a systemic effort to improve the quality of SORMAS data.

Surveillance was intensified at places of people gathering and the peripheral Local Government Areas. There was intense social mobilization and risk communication through radio jingles and use of information, education, and communication (IEC) materials, aims to educate different gender, age and social groups.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, evidence from this study showed that individuals in their active age group, *Almajiris* and living in urban areas had a high CFR. Based on this finding, we recommend that Jigawa Ministry of Health should intensify surveillance, social mobilization and risk communication at schools and commercial places, a potential place where younger age group are usually found to reduce morbidity and mortality especially among active age group. There is a need for NCDC to update the SORMAS software/platform, so that some defined fields are so important that one cannot proceed without filling them, so that proportion of missing information will be minimized. Jigawa State Government should promote

policies that reduce interaction with confirmed or suspected cases at the state, LGA, and community levels by the use of NCDC's guidelines. Further research should be conducted for better understanding of the disease.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We acknowledged Nigeria Center for Disease Control, Jigawa State Government Ministry of Health, World Health Organization, PHCDA, AFENET, UNICEF, MSF, Lafiya UK Projects and Women for Health.

Competing Interest

We declare no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this manuscript.

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